

greater data

July 2024

Building a shared approach to collecting, sharing and using data to drive better public service decision-making across the Liverpool City Region

The blueprint

A bit of context

In early 2024 we spoke to public, third sector and private partners from across the Liverpool City Region (LCR). We wanted to understand more about the things that drive stronger, shared, useful intelligence - and the things that get in the way. We heard about holes in data sets, the role of culture and policy around data sharing and the gaps in 'know how' when considering how data can be used and applied. We found a shared desire for a blueprint, a list of 'to-dos' that would get us to stronger, shared ways of working.

Over later months we pulled together our findings, grouping them into themes and building the bones of a plan for the region. In early June we brought our partners back together, spending the day workshopping the outline plan and sharing ideas. We asked, 'is this hitting the mark?', 'have we missed anything?' and 'is anything under or over-played?'. Together we tweaked, added, removed and polished the final content.

The result is a blueprint, a way for us to create a solid foundation on which to build a transformational approach that puts data at the heart of modern public services. We want to thank those who have contributed to this blueprint, (through conversations, workshops and "can I just run this past you" chats!) helping to design the principles needed to move forward into the next phase of greaterdata in the LCR.

“

Just like the coral reef, this work is about creating an environment which supports people to thrive. Things will only work if we allow the light in, share our combined efforts and create the conditions we need for better, more effective services.

Rachel Goldicutt, Careful Trouble

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Throughout this document, you'll see references to 'we', 'public services' and 'partners'. By this, we mean organisations who are working to plan and deliver services to local people and their communities. If you can add something to the delivery of the plan, we'd love to hear from you, please get in touch at cdc.info@liverpool.ac.uk.

A shared, overarching vision

What will things look like once we've succeeded?

In 5 years time we will have applied the principles in this blueprint to drive action and change. Across the Liverpool City Region, we will have built a shared, regional approach to working with data, an approach that focuses on action, an approach that's creating bigger, quicker, more visible impact on the transformation of our public services.

Our work will have removed 'system barriers' and refocused ways of working to include local people - putting them at the heart of decision-making, helping them to play their part in unlocking the power of data. This joined-up approach will have gathered huge momentum, will be built on trust, and led by an ever-growing network of people with shared ambitions - people who see the potential data holds to drive positive change.

“ We’ve got to build trust to make any progress in this space. Trust between organisations and communities, organisations to organisations... it’s just not there.”

To achieve this vision, we've grouped our 'work to be done' into five themes – this is '*what*' we'll do. In addition, we've developed an outline cultural framework to zoom in on '*how*' we'll do things.

We'll explain each of these parts in more detail over the next few pages.

The five parts of our blueprint:

greater**coordination**

greater**skillsets**

greater**tools**

greater**engagement**

greater**reflection**

Underpinned by a cultural framework...

greater**ways of working**

All held together by the golden thread of

greater**trust** that must run through this work.

**Our greaterdata
model for change**

greater
data

greater
ways of working

The culture we want to embed

This cultural framework outlines the key behaviours we need to grow our golden thread of **trust** and to make this blueprint tip into action.

We're committed to **doing this together**

- ✓ We want to move towards shared goals and away from siloed thinking.
- ✓ We want to ensure diverse representation and inclusion is prioritised.
- ✓ We understand and equally value the data shared by each partner.

We're open to doing **things differently**

- ✓ We remain flexible and take a responsive, 'push the boundaries' attitude.
- ✓ We're actively curious, we seek to understand and, when we need to, we're willing to change.
- ✓ We'll always ensure our work is focused on people's needs first and 'system' needs second.

We're driven by **positivity & possibility**

- ✓ We see data as an enabler for change, not a box-ticking exercise.
- ✓ We speak in the language of opportunities not the language of problems.
- ✓ We believe this approach can work, and we do everything possible to make it happen.

We're intent on **making progress**

- ✓ We're focused on continual learning.
- ✓ We appropriately deal with blockages in this work, we're not afraid to challenge them head on.
- ✓ We're proactive, acting wherever we can to support this plan.

Key actions:

This blueprint pulls together the key 'whats' - the jobs we need to do to create change. But to get things moving, below are some key actions we need to deliver on to build momentum in our new ways of working.

- ✓ We'll sign up partners from across LCR to this plan of action, encouraging them to show their commitment to the programme and share accountability around its delivery. This will include commitments to:
 - Engage with a greaterdata learning programme for leaders, supporting them to understand more about what we're trying to do and asking them to give this work resource and momentum.
 - Give and take constructive feedback as part of the programme to help all partners create change. This might include flagging barriers in certain organisational cultures, or cross-system ways of working and then working together to find ways to break them down.
 - Develop an internal engagement programme - using buddying and joint-working projects to build trust in one another and start to change the mindset from 'mine' to 'ours'.
- ✓ We'll form a network steering group, a core team of people who'll lead and shape the delivery of the greaterdata blueprint.
- ✓ We'll use action logs to ensure people are doing the things they agree to within this plan, ensuring we're continually making progress.
- ✓ We'll create safe spaces to feedback on what's working and what isn't and support partners to work through these challenges.
- ✓ We'll monitor our membership and engagement levels, developing an external engagement programme to recruit and retain members that create diverse and engaged representation from across sectors.
- ✓ We'll create reflection tools to improve how we work together including peer to peer sessions, 360 reviews on joint working and coaching opportunities.

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coordination

greater
skillsets

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engagement

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tools

greater
reflection

So now we've got our cultural framework outlined. Let's have a look at the five parts of our blueprint that make up the 'what'.

greater coordination

We need to build on our understanding around what is happening currently in the LCR data world. We need to dig deeper into the enablers and blockers that will impact our vision and work out what we need to do to coordinate this work.

greater coordination

Evaluating policy priorities:

We'll dig deeper into local, regional and national priorities, understanding the impact of their structure on the delivery of our blueprint.

- ✓ We'll identify shared priority areas and agree 'opportunity areas' of focus.
- ✓ We'll flag conflicting priorities across the region and work together to decide a way through.
- ✓ We'll explore the capabilities of systems already in use in the LCR and plan for linking up data pools across sectors.

Exploring the data that we already have available:

We'll start to understand the data we already hold across our partners, what it tells us, what gaps there are and how sharing it might add value. We'll also consider how it might be impacted by bias or the organisational lens it's been collated through.

- ✓ We'll coordinate a clear picture of available data across LCR informed by health and social care priorities.
- ✓ We'll identify gaps in representation across this existing data and work out how to fill these as a network.
- ✓ We'll understand current systems and their capabilities to see the tools we already hold as a region.

Finding the availability of people and pounds:

We'll understand what people-hours, skills and financial investment we have available working on themes within this plan. We'll then work out where there are gaps in human or financial resource and how might we work together to fill them.

- ✓ We'll map the job roles connected to this work across the city region and any availability within those posts to support the greaterdata project.
- ✓ We'll map investment in data related projects across LCR, understanding their purpose, end date and current progress.
- ✓ We'll create shared roles that promote the delivery of this blueprint.
- ✓ We'll develop a shared investment plan to access resource as a programme in a joined-up way and work together to build investment business cases (for direct delivery of his plan, but also key enablers for its success e.g. digital inclusion programmes).

greater skillsets

We need to think about the skills we have and need in our communities and across our professional teams to maximise the impact of this work.

greater skillsets

Maximising the skills of people living in the region:

We'll build understanding of how vital data sharing is for public service development and how critical people's input is to make sure our work has the right focus. We'll discuss data value and fears around data loss and help people understand the risks.

- ✓ We'll co-produce engaging community learning programmes around the power and value of data.
- ✓ We'll create communications campaigns that challenge misinformation around data sharing.
- ✓ We'll offer digital inclusion programmes to enhance digital skills and support projects which work on the 'basic' enablers.
- ✓ We'll work with partners to build skills for the future, developing a targeted learning programme and/or apprenticeships/ traineeships for young people to gain a greater understand of opportunities and support those wishing to work in the field of data or intelligence.

Understanding and challenging data bias:

We'll improve the understanding of those collecting, processing and analysing data around the risks of bias. We'll ensure reducing data bias is integrated into equality diversity and inclusion work and programmes across the region.

- ✓ We'll introduce learning programmes around bias relating to data.
- ✓ We'll improve representation within the core network and the steering group to ensure we continually 'check' ourselves from an inclusion point of view.
- ✓ We'll develop guidance/proposed actions for organisations on understanding and adapting to reduce bias in their approaches that can be added into existing equality, diversity and inclusion strategies/action plans.

“ **Young people are not aware that roles in data exist.**”

Maximising the skills of people working in the region:

We'll build data literacy and capacity across local organisations from the grassroots to anchor organisations. We'll support those working in the sector to understand greaterdata and their role within it. It's vital that everyone across each organisation has a common baseline so that we're all talking in the same language and to drive trust.

- ✓ We'll improve skills across a range of topics that are key for the success of greater data including:
 - What we mean by data and how it can be used
 - Systems and processes around data
 - Legal risks relating to data
 - Opportunities for innovation offered by data
 - Analysis and critical modelling - making decisions from data
 - Softer skills when working with data e.g. inquisitive approach, communication, ethics and inclusion.
- ✓ We'll create professional networks around key data related roles - including roles that are data gathering, processing or analysis specialists and also those that fall into wider job roles e.g. grassroots organisation founders, Heads of Quality or Assurance or even commissioning leads. Through this we'll create more opportunities for people to use these skills informally to benefit the network as a whole.
- ✓ We'll access funds to invest in apprenticeships, external learning programmes and mentoring for those organisations wishing to build their internal capabilities.

“It's important that organisations have uniformity in how they deliver learning around data and intelligence. By having similar approaches, we can easier build relationships and ensure comparable standards.”

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Leadership, information governance and improving data sharing:

We'll take a creative approach in supporting organisations to build data leadership and decision-making capability: understanding more about the practicalities of data sharing technically, legally and culturally.

- ✓ We'll offer coaching support to bring consistency and challenge to leaders where there are joint working opportunities and issues around information governance (IG).
- ✓ We'll deliver legal, ethical and governance learning programmes and 'art of the possible' in IG programmes around managing risk rather than letting it block sharing.
- ✓ We'll support cultural change programmes across the region and setup a working group with organisational development leads who can help us develop targeted pieces of work.
- ✓ We'll encourage organisations to offer more strategic, creative approaches to maximising skills, encouraging them to move away from 'box-ticking learning' around data to approaches that make people think differently.
- ✓ We'll deliver technical learning programmes around the practicalities of data sharing and setup working groups with technical leads across our network, focusing on how we can simplify this rather than create more complication or cost.

“ **When people have the skills, let them use them. We need to resource sufficiently for specialism and for teaching. If we pull people around the organisation we dilute what they can offer.”**

greater engagement

We need to think about engagement and how we actively involve people to share and deliver what's set out in this blueprint.

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Defining the 'pitch' to engage more voices:

We need to really think about why people might want to become involved in this work and how we get their buy-in, this will vary depending on where they are and what they do. We'll actively grow these participation and engagement opportunities.

- ✓ We'll build an inclusive brand with a shared narrative alongside our network of partners and local people. We'll use simple language around purpose, vision and objectives that everyone can align to whilst finding the best people to go forward and champion the greaterdata story.
- ✓ We'll develop a core communications plan which includes key messages by audience built around our understanding of the how the work might match to their ambitions and motivations.

For example:

- Local people will feel listened to.
- Commissioners will have the information needed to make effective decisions.
- Providers will have clear evidence of need and can use this to start new conversations with the public sector.
- Regional leaders will see LCR become an example best practice through this work.
- ✓ We'll keep a wide range of stakeholders engaged ensuring consistent representation across residents, local SMEs, the third sector and public sector. And we'll actively grow these engagement opportunities. We'll offer more opportunities for local people to get involved through participatory design, citizen's juries and data stewardship programmes.
- ✓ We'll demonstrate our analytical capabilities to local organisations and residents.
- ✓ We'll evidence our success through regular storytelling, evidencing small scale impact rather than waiting to share 'something big'.

greater engagement

Building confidence with local people:

If this work is going to be successful, we need to work with local people to understand what they want from the public sector, but also to recognise that it will take time to build this trust and confidence.

- ✓ We'll embed approaches to support ongoing conversations between communities and organisations around data and need.
- ✓ We'll communicate the story of their involvement, what it has achieved and why it's important to keep local people at the centre.
- ✓ We'll ensure the public facing engagement work is led by trusted people such as registered social landlords, charities or grassroots community organisations. We'll build the voice and brand of the work we're doing with these key partners.

Driving-up diversity:

We need to increase representation in the data we collect and in our decision making.

- ✓ We'll ensure our steering group network membership reflects the diversity of communities across LCR.
- ✓ We'll run targeted events and engagement projects across under-represented communities aiming to drive up understanding and inclusion relating to this work.

Strengthening relationships:

We'll foster links with key leaders locally and nationally using our work, and our shared intelligence to influence policy and strategy.

- ✓ We'll create opportunities for network building and connection between leaders across the public, private and third sectors at both strategic and operational levels.
- ✓ We'll focus on strengthening inter-organisational communication, facilitating this wherever we can across the network to maximise understanding and joint working.
- ✓ We'll play an active role in ensuring local, informed representation in consultations and working groups, nationally and locally.

greater tools

We know we have to look at the tools we use, this includes the key processes, job roles, systems and technology needed to make our vision a reality.

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Practically supporting adoption and scale-up:

We need to take an optimistic and ambitious approach to a shared way of doing things.

- ✓ We'll get to a place where we have shared, inclusive legal and governance structures; shared data standards, shared protocols and interoperability frameworks.
- ✓ We'll define clear roles and responsibilities across the network so we know what each organisation is doing to achieve our joint aims.
- ✓ We'll prioritise compatibility when purchasing or commissioning new systems, to make it easier to connect our datasets together.
- ✓ We'll create new, more effective processes of data collation, processing, analysis and sharing as a network.

Linking data into decision-making and service improvement:

We need to make sure that we build data around key areas of policy, themes around which want to have an impact.

- ✓ We'll explore joint strategic planning information, policy and analysis to identify key areas of opportunity for reform, innovation and investment. We'll then focus on these topics to build stronger connected sets of data.
- ✓ We'll develop a shared approach to understand, prioritise and then advocate for policy change locally and nationally.

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Maintaining high-quality and relevant data:

We collate data that is joined-up and easy to access for all sectors.

- ✓ We'll codesign a shared approach to data collection and trial a shared platform to bring together data from a range of organisations. We'll find funding for dedicated resource to maintain this.
- ✓ We'll work to standardise data across the system wherever possible to increase its accessibility and usefulness.
- ✓ We'll ensure that data collation and sharing is always two-way. Provider data will be incorporated into the shared platform alongside public sector data, so this becomes a true partnership committed to building data depth.
- ✓ We'll grow the sector's understanding around the potential of AI and the key role of large and quality datasets in its application.

We've got to do more to ensure that the value of the 'intelligence' from the ground is considered as part of our 'data' in our systems."

greater reflection

We need to consistently reflect on the implementation of this plan, this will allow us to continually develop and improve this work.

greater reflection

Critically evaluating impact:

We need to consider our approach to the evaluation of this work before it commences, this ensures we have an effective, rational and critical approach to assessing if we've achieved what we set out to.

- ✓ We'll develop a shared monitoring and evaluation framework at the outset that helps us measure the impact of our work. We'll include qualitative and quantitative elements alongside an independent evaluation function which focuses on:
 - KPIs around data quality, accessibility/sharing and availability (built from baseline data benchmarks).
 - Resident feedback on skills and engagement (including measures around curiosity relating to the 'use and power of data').
 - Wider stakeholder feedback on skills, engagement and practical tools.
 - Examples of data driven innovation - either where this work has inspired the creation of a solution or helped to tweak/test it.

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“**Too often reviews are ‘validations’ not ‘evaluations’ we need a genuine commitment, and the skills, to analyse and critically evaluate the work.”**

Tweaking and improving our approach:

We need to agree a shared approach to change as we go through this programme of work, accepting that our approach can never stay still and will likely require continuous adjustment.

- ✓ We'll develop a shared approach to adjust and improve our approach that will allow us to continue to grow its impact.
- ✓ We'll continually reflect on our outcomes, sense check them and wherever required adjusting them and the associated plan so we can best meet our vision.

“**We need to build in critical reflection in a continuous way.”**

How will we know if it's worked?

Our desired outcomes

Back to our overarching vision and the purpose of this work, we have a series of key themes:

- **Building a shared approach to working with data - gathering momentum through a shared network built on trust.**
- **Making a visible impact on the transformation of our public services - seeing the potential data holds to drive positive change.**
- **Putting local people at the heart of decision-making.**

On the next page we outline a basic model of how we believe this work will support us in achieving this vision. We'll continue to work with local people and partners to capture current and future activity, making sure that we have a real-time and clear view of all the great things happening across the region to achieve the greaterdata goals.

Building a shared approach to working with data / Gathering momentum through a shared network built on trust:

THE PRACTICAL ACTION

Putting local people at the heart of decision-making:

Making a visible impact on the transformation of our public services / Seeing the potential data holds to drive positive change:

THE PRACTICAL ACTION

What might stop us?

Central to the success of driving the activities in this blueprint is the understanding of barriers and potential risks that could stop us creating the impact we wish to. The below 'mini key risk register' acts as an overview to some of the key themes the greaterdata steering group will need to consider and mitigate to ensure we succeed.

KEY RISK

We only deliver parts of this plan, missing key 'buckets of work'.

If we only deliver part of the blueprint, we'll not achieve the change we want to across the region. This is because much of this plan is highly interdependent. For example, without cultural change we won't have people using the tools we build, or if we don't have engagement of communities, we will still have gaps in vital datasets.

THOUGHTS ON MITIGATION

High-level oversight from the greaterdata steering group with accountability held by CDC.

KEY RISK

Organisations don't fully commit to this way of working and continuing to work in silos.

It will take time to build trust and therefore move over to a more inclusive way of working. Funding silos and governance structures drive independent behaviour in addition to pre-existing organisational strategies.

THOUGHTS ON MITIGATION

Funders need to work together with the greaterdata team to align with the desired work within this plan. Senior leadership (Board level) buy-in is needed from key partners to ensure internal accountability around joint working.

KEY RISK

Mixed messages create confusion.

By not using the shared narrative, simple language and joined-up approach to engagement, confusion is created across key groups (most likely across local people and the third sector).

THOUGHTS ON MITIGATION

Engagement in the co-production of the shared brand, communications plan and messaging so that all members feel comfortable in moving to that narrative.

KEY RISK

Tools and platforms developed need to work for all members of the network.

If we don't design tools that work for everyone in the network, we risk missing out on some intelligence and also reducing the access to available data for some organisations. This would reduce the impact of the work overall.

THOUGHTS ON MITIGATION

The development of any tool or platform needs to be led by insight from the wider network including technical skills, existing data availability, compatibility of systems and also time available to commit to this work.

Before you go...

During the development of this blueprint, two things have become very clear, facts that we need to hold on to as we start to deliver on it:

1 We have to make sure our approach to data and intelligence is and remains locally led. We as partners in the LCR region must own this shared approach and if necessary, challenge it, change it and champion it.

2

There is no 'one-size-fits-all' approach to data innovation. This isn't something we're going to see rolled out by national government to create a cut and paste 'fix'. This is bespoke and we can roll in a way that works for our region.

We hope this blueprint reflects the local energy and desire for change in LCR and excites you around the true potential we have as a network to drive change in the region.

Through this shared plan we want to grow our local network across all sectors - private, public and third, whilst giving reassurance that this approach is stewarded and enabled by local public service bodies, organisations who truly want to make the region a leader in data led decision-making and change.

Like all good conversations, this one needs to continue, and we want more people to join in, to listen, to share and to make things happen. Fancy getting in on the action? Email us at cdc.info@liverpool.ac.uk and we'll get you on board.

Who are the Civic Data Cooperative?

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The Liverpool City Region Civic Data Cooperative (LCR CDC) is a data governance project funded by the Liverpool City Region Combined Authority (LCRCA) and hosted by the Faculty of Health and Life Sciences at the University of Liverpool.

We work closely with the public sector, businesses and academic organisations, including System P and CIPHA. Our collective work aims to create an environment where data can be accessed, linked and analysed securely for the benefit of society, and provide guidance to researchers, industry experts, and the public in relation to data use.

Our role is to connect organisations, and citizens, in our region to appropriate data in order to help improve service delivery and solve big problems.

We want to create a vibrant, internationally visible, civic data environment which will enable residents' data to work harder for them to shape better care and fuel globally important innovations from the Liverpool City Region. Based on a collaborative, transparent and inclusive approach to governance, the Civic Data Cooperative will support people and organisations to:

- Understand and act on the insights from civic data
- Provide innovative solutions to real-life problems
- Facilitate access to open sources of civic data
- Test models for ethical, inclusive use of health data

Through this collaborative process, we believe we can encourage positive health and well-being changes across the Liverpool City Region.

Find out more at civicdatacooperative.com

Who are Capacity?

It's no secret that the public and third sectors are facing some tough internal and external challenges, and we need big ideas and brave leaders to tackle them.

That's where Capacity comes in. We provide the know-how, big-picture thinking, and hands-on time to get moving on the projects that really matter: the ones that make the biggest impact on the lives of everyday people.

In other words, you might call us a 'do-tank'. Unlike a think-tank, we also go on to do the stuff we've thought about. That means we're on the journey with the organisations we support; you won't find us producing a shiny report and leaving them to it.

We also believe we're better off together. By that we mean: we want all sectors involved and all sectors represented. We aren't going to change public services for the better on our own, and neither is anyone else.

Speaking of teamwork, our people are a total mix - we all have different backgrounds and a wide range of expertise. That means we can apply a range of skills and viewpoints to the challenges we face and fill any gaps a team might have.

Ultimately, we want the North West to be the best place to grow-up, grow-wise and grow-old. If we do this well, public services will work for every person, every time. And as for us? Well, we'll be out of job.

Find out more at thiscapacity.co.uk

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To find out more about this work or get involved contact:

cdc.info@liverpool.ac.uk

